

Physiological disorders of tomato and their management

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Abstract

Tomato is one of the important crop in the family solanaceae. It is the third most important cultivated crop in India but it is adversely affected by various abiotic factors. This article will help growers in understanding various physiological disorders that impact the crop, and remedies which should be followed to control them. The major physiological disorders which are affecting the crop are blossom end rot, fruit cracking (radial and concentric cracking), puffiness, sunscald, blotchy ripening etc., The visible symptoms of the blossom end rot affected fruits are showing small darkened or water soaked area near the blossom end of the fruit which is majorly caused due to Calcium deficiency. Fruit cracking is associated with cracks develop at the stem end of the fruit, due to heavy rainfall or irrigation followed by long dry spell. The fruits affected with puffiness are looks normal from outside, but the fruit are hollow inside. One of the seed cavities is usually empty. Causes of puffiness are extreme high or low temperature, excessive fertilization and poor pollination and fertilization. Sunscald occurs on fruit exposed to the sun during periods of extreme heat and the affected fruits are shiny white or yellow patches would be on the sides of the fruit exposed to the sun. So this article will help the growers on various physiological disorders which are affecting the crop and the remedial measures to be followed to grow the healthy crop.

Introduction

Tomato occupies a prime position in list of protective foods since it is a rich source of minerals like calcium sodium (12.9 mg), trace elements, copper (0.19 mg), vitamins like vitamin A (900 IU), vitamin C (27 mg), vitamin B complex (thiamine), essential amino acids and healthy organic acids like citric, formic and acetic acids. The attractive red colour of fruit is due to lycopene and yellow colour is due to carotenes. The leading tomato growing states are UP, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Haryana, Punjab and Bihar. Several processed items like paste, puree, syrup, juice, ketchup, drinks etc are prepared on large scale. Some times, it is called poor man's orange.

color, shape, size, hardness, texture, dry matter, organoleptic, and nutraceutical characteristics all play a role in determining tomato fruit quality for fresh eating (Dorais et al., 2001). Tomatoes should be free of physiological problems not just for decorative purposes, but also because other characteristics, such as nutritional status and shelf life, may be influenced. Physiological or abiotic diseases are mostly caused by changing environmental circumstances such as temperature, moisture, imbalanced soil nutrients, insufficient or excessive amounts of specific soil minerals, soil pH extremes, and poor drainage (Khavari-Nejad et al., 2009). Genetic factors have a role in this. Blossom-end rot, catface, growth cracks, sunscald, yellow shoulder, chemical damage, adventitious root, puffiness, blotchy ripening, gold spots/ specks, and chilling injury are the most common physiological problems that affect tomatoes. The crop's productivity is severely harmed by these illnesses. Therefore, the understanding the symptoms, cause

and management is necessary which is discussed below:

1. Blossom end rot

Brown water soaked discoloration appears at the blossom end of the fruit where the senescent petals are attached while the fruit is still green. The spots enlarge and darken rapidly and the affected portion of the fruit becomes sunken, leathery and dark coloured. Development of grey to black discoloration of epidermis of fruit.

Causes

Imbalance of magnesium and potassium. High soil and moisture and high temperature. Moisture stress conditions. Deficiency of calcium in the **Blossom end rot**

Control 1. Give light and frequent irrigation to maintain optimum soil moisture. 2. Apply recommended quantity of nitrogen. 3. Spray crop with calcium chloride (0.5%) at fruit development stage.

2. Fruit cracking:

Two types of cracking occur in tomato fruit (Radial and Concentric cracking). Concentric cracking is a splitting of the epidermis in circular patterns around the stem scar. Radial cracking is a splitting that radiates toward the blossom end from the stem scar. Radial cracking is more likely to develop in full ripe fruit than in mature green. Fruits exposed to sun develop more concentric cracking than those, which are covered with foliage. Cracks occur on tomatoes as they near maturity, depending on the cultivar. Less susceptible cultivars do not crack until the breaker stage; more tolerant cultivars do not crack until they are red ripe; resistant cultivars rarely crack at all. Cracking is associated with rapid fruit development and wide fluctuations in water availability to the plant. Fruit that has reached the

ripening stage during dry weather may show considerable cracking if the dry period is followed by heavy rains and high temperatures.

Cause 1. Long dry spell during rainy season. 2. Moisture stress condition due to irregular irrigation. Sudden fluctuation in day and night temperature. 3. Exposure of fruit to sunlight. 4. Boron deficiency in soil.

Control 1. Maintain optimum soil moisture through light irrigation. 2. Avoid pruning and staking of plants during summer. 3. Grow resistant varieties like Sioux, Punjab Chuhara, Pusa Ruby, Roma, Pant T-1, Arka Saurabh etc. 4. Spray borax @ 0.3 to 0.4% two to three times. 5. Harvest the fruits before they ripe fully.

3. Puffiness: The outer wall of the fruit is normal, but the tomato is hollow inside. One of the seed cavities is usually empty. Cause: Extreme high or low temperatures, excessive nitrogen fertilization, and heavy rains may interfere with normal pollination, resulting in puffy fruit. Puffiness occurs most frequently on early fruit. (Richard Jauron, 1997) [5] . Control: No effective controls. Puffiness should decline later in the summer. Optimum dosage of fertilizers should be applied to minimize the disorder.

4. Sunscald: Green fruits exposed to direct sunlight ripen unevenly so that yellow patches appear on the side of the tomato fruit when it ripens. Symptoms are most likely to appear at the mature green to breaker stage of development. The lesions are infected by secondary infection of fungus which shows black dark spots making tomatoes unfit for consumption. Sunscald caused due to High fruit pericarp temperature 40C. In bright sunlight, surface temperature may be more than 10C highest than the air temperature. (K.L. Chada, 2001).

Control: The best protection against sunscald is to utilize cultivars with enough foliage to cover the fruit and to provide enough water and pest protection to maintain the healthy foliage. Crop are planted at higher densities are less susceptible to this malady. Cultivation of indeterminate /semideterminate varieties without staking also could be helpful.

5. Cate Face The affected fruits are characterized by the distortion of the blossom end rot and development of ridge, furrow indentations and blotches

Causes Unfavorable climatic conditions during flowering cause distortion of growth of the pistil cells.

Control 1. Grow varieties free from this disorder. 2. Cultivation condition makes favorable as much as possible by adopting appropriate and timely management.

6. Blotchy ripening: This disorder also known as the gray wall is recognized as grayish appearance caused by partial collapse of the wall tissue hence the term gray wall. The affected area remain green or yellow are usually found nearly at the stem end of the tomato fruit. It was due to the deficiency of potassium (K). (Lalit Kumar Verma et al, 2018)

Control: Use of balanced fertilizer dose (after soil testing) in the crop prevents the occurrence of blotchy ripening. Adjust the planting date to achieve favorable light intensity for good fruit development.

7. Chemical injury: Major chemical damages to tomatoes are caused by herbicides. A common herbicide injury problem in tomatoes is caused by phenoxy herbicides such as 2,4-D and dicamba. These are hormone-type herbicides that are common components of products used to control broadleaf weeds in lawns, pastures and grain crops. These herbicides are prone to drift or move with water to non-target sites. Symptoms of phenoxy herbicide injury appear primarily as a distortion of new growth that occurs following exposure to the herbicide. Young leaves do not fully expand, are narrow and pointed, and tend to curl downward

Control: To avoid herbicide injury, spray of the herbicide should be avoided when wind may carry spray drift toward tomatoes or other sensitive crops. Also, herbicide spray should be with low pressures coarse spray nozzle, and spray should be applied as close to the ground as possible.

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